

Welcome Pack

An onboarding guide for
RDA Working Groups

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Introduction

The welcome pack for RDA WGs (planned or endorsed) receiving support via RDA TIGER aims to offer a comprehensive and user-friendly guide. It includes essential RDA information, important templates, and key documents supporting all RDA-related activities throughout the lifespan of WG.

Get to know RDA

A quick introduction to the Research Data Alliance (RDA), highlighting the mission and vision behind the organisation and the several advisory and administrative groups that support the day-to-day operations.

- First glance
 - ◆ [RDA Overview](#)
 - ◆ [RDA Governance](#)

What RDA TIGER offers

A concise introduction to the RDA TIGER project, highlighting key TIGER offerings and services available for Working Groups. Explore the services portfolio and the financial mechanisms supporting RDA Working Groups via the links below.

- [RDA TIGER Support](#)
- Introducing [RDA TIGER](#)
 - ◆ [Support Services for RDA Working Groups](#): Facilitation, Communications, Landscape Analysis & Output Support Services

- ◆ Financial support mechanisms
 - RDA TIGER Cascading Grants
The RDA Europe is running a call for proposals to enhance the activities of its Working Groups, including the adoption and further development of the Working Group outputs. The call is open for any entity eligible to receive Horizon Europe funding that is not a consortium member of the RDA TIGER project — more on how you can apply [here](#).
 - RDA TIGER Support for externally provided actions for the Working Group.
 - The WG may require specific expertise or roles to support its activities. Examples include (but are not limited to) hiring experts, data

collection, interviews, analysis, graphical design, or authoring and editing large documents. In these contexts, the WG identifies a specific kind of expertise and describes this in their application. You can apply via the rolling open call; more details [here](#).

- ◆ [Contribution to the EOSC](#)

RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB) and RDA Annotator

The RDA-KB aims to make it simpler and more useful to look for, link to, access, and re-use RDA outputs and supplementary resources. Secondly, it aims to make it simpler and more effective to classify, curate, publish, and preserve outputs and resources. The RDA-KB contains a graph database of outputs, individuals, and other resources from the RDA and associated organisations, making it simple to link them to each other. The RDA Annotator is a browser plugin that allows you to annotate and tag web resources using RDA Vocabularies, making them available to the community through the RDA-KB.

- [RDA Discovery demo](#) (search and discovery of RDA-KB data)
- [RDA Annotator Guidelines](#) (including installation guide), and [demonstration](#) (including recording).

Disclaimer: Please note that this beta version is meant as a demonstration. The final version of the RDA Knowledge Base will follow in the coming months.

RDA WGs

Here you can find useful resources for Working Groups (WGs), including guidance on starting, managing, and finalising WGs, such as case statement templates, work plans, and information on RDA Plenaries and Birds of a Feather sessions.

- Groups Overview: the driving force of RDA
[RDA Working Groups](#) (WGs) should tangibly accelerate progress in concrete ways for specific communities with the overarching goal of increasing data-driven innovation. Efforts are intended to promote data sharing and exchange, interoperability, data use and reuse, data discoverability and analysis, data stewardship and preservation, and best practices for substantive communities.
 - ◆ [Creating & Joining RDA WGs](#): Getting started, Working period, Finalisation and results
 - ◆ [RDA Group Chairs Roles and Responsibilities](#)
- WG Outputs & Recommendations
RDA Outputs are the technical and social infrastructure solutions developed by RDA Working Groups (WG), Interest Groups (IG) or Communities of Practice (CoP). These Outputs have an important impact in two areas: solving problems,

and incorporation and/or adoption in infrastructure environments by individuals, projects and organisations.

- ◆ [Recommendations & Outputs: Definitions & Examples](#)
- ◆ [Recommendations & Supporting Outputs Guidelines](#)
- ◆ [Adoption stories](#)

→ Resources Hub

◆ Drafting your Case Statement

- [WG Case Statement Development](#)
- [Case Statement Template](#)
- Recruiting Group Members

Ensure membership represents at least 2, but preferably 3 or more continents, and comprises multiple sectors/disciplines and roles.

◆ Shared WG workspace

- [Communication plan template](#)
- [Meeting notes template](#)

→ Broader RDA community

- ◆ WGs are focused, time-limited activities aiming at producing specific, tangible outputs. The impact of these outputs is greatly enhanced by engagement with the broader RDA community: Interest Groups, Communities of Practice and organisations RDA has close links with (such as ReSA or CODATA). RDA TIGER services can help you identify groups and organisations that can increase the impact of your working group.

◆ RDA Plenaries

Plenaries are RDA's flagship events held twice per year, one hybrid event in a different place around the world and one completely virtual. Plenary meetings are special working events that help move the community forward in creating tangible deliverables that improve data sharing across disciplines, technologies, and countries. Plenaries provide an excellent opportunity for formal and informal interaction and engagement with other WGs, interest groups, organisations, and communities RDA works closely with. Discovering individuals and initiatives with shared interests can form the basis for new interdisciplinary collaborations and innovations.

- Planned, future and past plenaries [information](#)
- Plenary submission form template – dynamic, please consult the forms shared for the specific plenary iteration.

Quickstart Checklist for RDA WGs

The RDA TIGER project guides and supports through each of the steps below, from coordination and facilitation to communication, funding mechanisms, and community engagement.

→ Confirm the core structure

- Co-chairs and their responsibilities agreed
- WG Case Statement endorsed (*or final draft under review*)
- Assigned TIGER support roles (facilitator, communications, etc.)

→ Set Up Your Collaboration Spaces

- RDA WG webpage/workspace is active
- Shared document space selected (RDA group webpage/ Drive / etc.)
- Communication channels agreed (WG RDA webpage / Teams / Slack / Zoom)

→ Organise the Kick-off

- Schedule WG launch call (template agenda available in this pack)
- Establish meeting rhythm and note-taking format
- Reconfirm scope, timeline, and expected outputs

→ Activate Support Services

- Identify which TIGER services you'll use and apply:
 1. Facilitation
 2. Communications
 3. Landscape Analysis
 4. Output Support

→ Position Your Group in the Wider RDA Community

- Map relevant Interest Groups / Communities of Practice to collaborate with
- Note key RDA Plenary dates and submission deadlines

Navigating RDA

In this section, you can find a comprehensive list of definitions and acronyms specific to the Research Data Alliance (RDA). This guide is designed to help members quickly understand the key terms and organisational structures integral to navigating RDA's activities.

- [RDA for Newcomers*](#)
- [RDA Pathways](#)
- [RDA Persona Quiz](#)

* RDA frequently organises dedicated online, hybrid and in-person events specifically designed for newcomers. Make sure to stay up-to-date by visiting the [events section](#) and signing up for the [newsletter](#).

RDA/RDA TIGER Branding toolbox

Essential resources for effectively utilising the RDA and RDA TIGER branding assets, including logo variations, presentation templates, and promotional materials for all your RDA-related communications and presentations.

- [RDA Communications Toolkit](#)
- Logos
 - ◆ [RDA Endorsement and Logo Usage Guidelines](#)
 - ◆ [RDA TIGER logo variations](#)
- Presentation templates
 - ◆ [RDA PowerPoint template](#)
- [Posters & Flyers](#): past flyers, posters and templates

Feedback

The RDA TIGER project pioneered professional support services to empower and assist RDA WGs in finalising their recommendations and outputs for the global community. We are committed to continuously refining our services to meet the changing needs of these groups, and we value your input through ongoing evaluation.

Share your experience and feedback by filling out the feedback [form](#).

Contact us

[The RDA Europe TIGER team members](#)

[RDA Secretariat](#)

research data sharing without barriers

rd-alliance.org